

When the gallbladder is gone, but the pain carries on – a review of clinical features and radiologic findings in Postcholecystectomy Syndrome

Learning objectives

This review aims to equip readers with a comprehensive understanding of the varied aetiologies, clinical manifestations and pertinent radiological findings associated with post-cholecystectomy syndrome (PCS).

Background

Post-cholecystectomy syndrome refers to the persistence of biliary colic or right upper quadrant pain along with a constellation of gastrointestinal symptoms after a cholecystectomy, which are similar to features experienced by patients pre-operatively. The aetiology of post-cholecystectomy syndrome is multifactorial, encompassing persistent or de novo gastrointestinal symptoms in 5-40% of patients. While the cause can be identified and managed in majority of cases, it often goes unexplained in one-third of patients³. Early complications such as bile duct injuries, leaks and vascular trauma arise shortly after the procedure, whilst late complications such as retained gallstones or bile duct strictures often present later on¹².

- **Biliary causes** of PCS are often attributed to anatomical and physiological changes that occur after the procedure, leading to altered bile flow dynamics and the potential for residual pathology. These include bile duct injuries, retained gallstones in the common bile duct or a cystic duct remnant⁹. Additionally, sphincter of Oddi dysfunction, characterized by an obstruction to bile flow at the ampulla of Vater, is a recognised biliary aetiology for PCS, contributing to pain and obstructive symptoms¹³.
- **Extra-biliary causes** in contrast often involve functional gastrointestinal disorders such as irritable bowel syndrome and functional dyspepsia, which if pre-existed, can be exacerbated by the physiological changes post-cholecystectomy¹³.

The clinical presentation of PCS is highly variable. Physical examination findings as well as are often non-specific due to the wide array of potential causes, emphasizing the importance on a detailed patient history and utilization of advanced imaging. Biochemical markers such as liver function tests, pancreatic enzyme levels and inflammatory markers can provide indirect evidence of biliary obstruction, pancreatic involvement or inflammation. The term *post-cholecystectomy syndrome* should be used as a provisional diagnosis whilst the aetiology of pain is unclear and should be replaced once further workup has identified the underlying pathology.

Imaging findings

Imaging is an essential, non-invasive tool to differentiate between normal post-operative anatomy and a potential new pathology. Based on the indication and suspected pathology, biliary ultrasound and computerized tomography (CT) are used primarily to investigate post-surgical complications. Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) is the modality of choice to structurally evaluate the biliary tree. Hepatobiliary specific contrast agents can be used in conjunction with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) to identify a bile leak postoperatively⁶.

Transabdominal ultrasonography is typically the initial imaging modality for evaluating PCS due to non-invasive nature, cost-effectiveness and the ability to visualise the biliary tree for post operative changes. It can identify stones in the common bile duct, residual gallstones in the cystic duct remnant and non-specific bile duct dilatation (>8mm), which are critical indicators of PCS. Despite its utility, ultrasonography may have limitations in detecting small stones or subtle biliary changes, necessitating further advanced imaging in cases of persistent symptoms¹³.

Fig 2: Transabdominal ultrasound showing dilated common bile duct (1cm) with obstructive cause. (Image courtesy of Jayanth Keshavamurthy, Radiopaedia.org, rID:72053)

Computerized tomography scans offer superior spatial resolution compared to ultrasound for evaluating the upper abdomen, particularly in assessing the pancreatic head, duodenal wall and retroperitoneal space to assess for extrinsic compression or other non-biliary causes of PCS. CT imaging can also identify inflammatory changes or neoplastic processes that might contribute to PCS symptoms. Multidetector CT angiography can further delineate vascular anomalies or ischemic changes contributing to post-cholecystectomy symptoms¹².

Magnetic Resonance Cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) is a non-invasive imaging technique that provides detailed visualisation of the biliary and pancreatic ducts without the need for intravenous contrast or ionising radiation, making it particularly useful for diagnosing bile duct injuries and retained stones in the paediatric and pregnant populations. MRCP with hepatobiliary contrast agents further enhances diagnostic accuracy by distinguishing between biliary and non-biliary fluid collections and identifying the source of bile leaks, including accessory ducts like the duct of Luschka¹. Furthermore, MRCP has demonstrated high sensitivity (96-100%) and specificity in detecting choledochal cysts¹⁰.

Fig 3: Coronal T2 weighted MRI abdomen showing a cyst like lesion (green arrow) below the anatomical location of the gallbladder after resection. Hyperdense cystic structure contains few small low-signal filling defects suggestive of gallstones. (Image courtesy of Mohammad Taghi Niknejad, Radiopaedia.org, rID:157627)

Fig 4: MRI abdomen T2 weighted fat saturated sequence showing hyperdense cystic duct remnant (green arrow) with low-signal defects within suggestive of gallstones. (Image courtesy of Mohammad Taghi Niknejad, Radiopaedia.org, rID:157627)

Endoscopic ultrasound (EUS) offers high-resolution imaging of the biliary and pancreatic ducts, providing superior diagnostic accuracy for microlithiasis, subtle strictures and periampullary lesions that may be missed by other modalities. It is particularly useful for categorizing the morphology of the papilla and distal common bile duct. The utility of EUS further extends to guiding fine-needle aspiration or biopsy of suspicious lesions, thereby facilitating definitive diagnosis and therapeutic planning².

Radionuclide scans, particularly hepatobiliary iminodiacetic acid scans, are functional studies that provide insights into the physiological aberrations contributing to PCS, particularly in cases where anatomical obstructions are absent¹⁴. Furthermore, scintigraphy can effectively identify bile leaks or fistulas that may not be apparent on other imaging modalities⁴.

Conclusion

The management of post-cholecystectomy syndrome is multifaceted, focusing primarily on addressing the underlying aetiology identified through comprehensive diagnostic workup, which has now evolved significantly, incorporating advanced imaging and endoscopic techniques. The continuity of research into novel diagnostic biomarkers and less invasive therapeutic modalities holds promise for improving patient outcomes and subsequent quality of life in this complex clinical entity.

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